

Satyagraha and Non-Violence means Mahatma Gandhi

Prof. Dr. Nitin Bawle

Head, History Department, Sharda Mahavidyalaya, Parbhani 431401 Maharashtra, India

Corresponding author E-mail: bawalenitin@gmail.com

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On August 15, 1947, Indians gained independence after a long struggle against the British. During the Mughal period, the British, who came as traders to the Indian region, established control over many powers through trade and political intervention. Due to different strategies of the British, many states came under their control. But gradually many of his policies started causing injustice to the Indian people. These injustices were political, social, religious and economic in nature. The injustices and atrocities inflicted by the British on India were of a harsher nature. The consequences of which India has to suffer even today. Apparently planetary wars, revolutions, invasions, conquests and famines are violent in nature and take longer. It had no effect on the Indians. But the victory achieved by the British changed the structure of Indian society. The previous invasion had no effect on the Indian economy, social order. On the contrary, it became very much integrated with Indian life. On the contrary, the British Empire destroyed the very foundation of India's social system and economy. These people remained in India as aliens and continued to collect taxes through one or the other means.¹ Many times Indians raised their voice in this protest, some organizations were also formed against the injustice. The anti-British struggle took different paths. Such struggles were also led by many. But Mohandas Karamchand Gandhi led the anti-British struggle in a very new way. Mohandas was born on 2 October 1869 and died on 30 January 1948. Mohandas is known as Mahatma Gandhi not only in India but throughout the world due to his significant contribution to Indian independence. All religions like Vedanta, Jainism, Buddhism, Christianity, Islam, Sikhism can be seen in Mahatma Gandhi's thought. The Indian freedom struggle intensified through his various anti-British movements. Indians demanded their rights from the British through petitions. But in terms of humanity, the British did injustice and atrocities without considering the Indians.

After achieving success against injustice in South Africa, Mahatma Gandhi returned to India in 1915. His successful fight against a tyrannical and tyrannical government in South Africa made his name universal in India. People here were curious about their unique way of unarmed resistance like

satyagraha. Hence, as soon as Gandhiji returned to India, people had great expectations about him. 2 This led Gandhi to adopt new ways while building the anti-British struggle. These new ways of Gandhiji continued to get the support of the people either past or future. People started participating in the struggle led by Gandhiji in large numbers. The leadership of all the anti-British struggle came to Gandhiji and under the guidance of Gandhiji, many movements like non-cooperation movement, satyagraha movement, civil disobedience movement, Chale Jav movement were started all over India. Gandhiji showed new ways for every movement. Satyagraha movement was raised for our true demand, non-cooperation movement was raised if the government was not doing its job, civil disobedience movement was raised against such law if the law was doing injustice to the people, and the injustice being done to Indians by the British is beyond tolerance, so please leave our country now. The Go back movement was established. Thus Gandhi used the path of truth and non-violence strongly and forcefully while leading the Indian freedom movement.

Gandhi stopped the oppression of the British by presenting the path of truth or insistence of truth to the British. According to Gandhiji the emancipation of oppressed people and the entire world depends entirely on truth and non-violence. There is no reason to doubt this. According to Gandhiji, complete non-violence is not for a few people but for the entire human race. 3 While doing satyagraha, if the British resist, they will give it without any resistance if they do injustice. Satyagraha is the insistence of the truth to someone through peaceful means without resorting to violent acts to demand it. This can change the other person's mind. Gandhiji believed in this. Satyagraha is an effective weapon of resistance not for the weak but for the calm, thoughtful, temperate, courageous, brave and fearless person. A coward cannot do Satyagraha but even a very ordinary person who is crushed in body but very strong in mind can raise a fight against any mighty power or government in the world and the effect is more effective than a gun bullet. Gandhiji guided everyone for this. Satyagraha is the best way to express your anti-British sentiments in a non-violent way, says Gandhiji. Many times Mahatma Gandhi challenged the British to do individual satyagraha or collective satyagraha to defeat their demands for justice. While doing Satyagraha, we used to present our views to the government through applications, requests, and we used to do Satyagraha and stick to our thoughts until success. On the whole, soft-minded people in Indian politics have not succeeded. But Gandhiji, in a soft but non-violent way, forced the British to yield to his demand for justice. The movement of Satyagraha led by Gandhiji continued to receive spontaneous support from all over India. Because the government was also forced to think before Satyagraha. As the injustice and oppressive attitude of the government came to light, the path of Satyagraha became popular and accepted by all. In Gandhi's satyagraha philosophy, Gautama Buddha's non-violence and Sri Krishna's non-violence of resistance to injustice are seen to be combined. Gandhi believed that Satyagraha is a more effective way than strike. But he was of the opinion that the one who does injustice to the same extent gets tired. Ethics must be a virtue in satyagrahas. In fact, if there is no morality, there can be no Satyagraha. Gandhiji also said that Satyagraha gains social prestige due to the establishment of morality. Satyagraha, led by Gandhiji, took the form of a movement. This satyagraha movement became a sweat for the British government. Because the satyagrahi participating in this used to endure any injustice of the British and stood firm on his demand. The number of satyagrahis increased day by day.

Whatever is needed can be obtained more quickly and more surely by satyagraha than by political power, the truth of which may be easily realized. 5 As Gandhiji's anti-British stand was based on the test of truth, Gandhiji decided to fight the entire anti-British struggle in a non-violent way. Gandhi's non-violence means that he stood firm on his demands without resorting to any kind of violence in the anti-

British struggle. Violent struggle does nothing but makes it worse whereas non-violent struggle makes something happen and even if it doesn't, nothing gets worse, that is the peculiar alchemy of Satyagraha.⁶ The non-violent ideas propounded by Gandhiji have great power. Because non-violence is never defeated, violence can be defeated, Gandhiji believed. That is why Gandhiji says that while practicing non-violence we should practice non-violence in many ways. We can achieve our work by practicing non-violence for different reasons in different ways such as constructive non-violence, prohibitive non-violence, absolute non-violence and moral non-violence. Gandhi also says that non-violence is the best force and it is self-force and we should use that divine force for our work. Gandhiji had proved the effectiveness of non-violence in many areas in his own life. But using their experiences, people like us after them cannot do the thing of non-violence. This is Gandhi's challenge to history, generally to the suffering of all the worlds. We will probably not be able to do as much and in the same way that they successfully pursued non-violence. But the more non-violently we fight the small and big violence of our neighbors, the more our partnership will be recorded in the history of humanity of this world. ⁷ While building the anti-British struggle, Gandhiji taught the entire Indian people the basic mantra of insisting on truth i.e. Satyagraha. Gandhiji strictly adhered to the principle that the struggle should be carried out in a non-violent way while the anti-British struggle was taking place.

Conclusion

1. Mahatma Gandhi brought the British to power by doing Satyagraha.
2. The demands of the Indian people were accepted through Satyagraha.
3. The philosophy of Satyagraha was rooted in the minds of all common people.
4. Mahatma Gandhi proved that every fight can be fought non-violently.
5. Mahatma Gandhi showed that the heart of a violent person can be changed through non-violent means.
6. Satyagraha and Ahimsa have become precious words for the world today Satyagraha and Ahimsa is Mahatma Gandhi.

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